

3D Pose Estimation Using a Global and Local Cross-Attention Mechanism

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Abstract—The task of 3D human pose and shape estimation involves the accurate prediction of 3D joint coordinates using a single image or a video sequence and it is crucial in several computer vision fields, such as sign language recognition, human-computer interaction and autonomous vehicles. Existing methodologies typically rely on modeling global and local temporal relationships among image frames without paying much attention to the interaction between these relationships and the modeling of the input space in other manifolds that possess important statistical and geometrical properties. This work proposes a novel multi-stage 3D pose estimation method that seamlessly combines global and local temporal modeling through self-attention mechanisms operating on multiple manifolds, thus leveraging the ability of different manifolds to model complementary features of the input space. Through the extraction of global and local attention maps and the fusion of these maps using a novel cross-attention mechanism, the proposed method aims to enhance the contextual understanding and improve the capacity of the model to capture the intricate human motion dynamics present in a video sequence. The effectiveness of the proposed method in achieving precise 3D pose and shape across successive frames is confirmed by the experimental results on two challenging datasets, namely 3DPW and MPI-INF-3DHP.

Index Terms—3d human pose and shape estimation; attention; manifold

I. INTRODUCTION

3D human pose and shape estimation concerns the estimation of the 3D joint coordinates and/or body parameters of a human body based on the processing of single images or image sequences. It comprises a vital research area with a diverse set of applications in various fields, such as gesture recognition [27], sign language recognition [1], [17], augmented reality/virtual reality [26], autonomous vehicles [34], human ergonomics [3], [18] and human-computer interaction [12].

In recent years, deep learning techniques have significantly advanced human pose estimation. Methods for 3D human pose and shape estimation can be categorized as either model-based, utilizing predefined parametric models like SMPL [22], or model-free, directly predicting 3D pose and shape without predefined structures. Model-based approaches [4], [10], [14], [15], [28], [30], [33] yield anatomically plausible estimations but are sensitive to initialization and struggle with complex poses or occlusions. On the other hand, model-free methods [16], [20] require extensive training data to learn the mapping between input and the corresponding 3D poses, yet they offer adaptability to different body shapes and poses. Nonetheless, 3D human pose estimation presents significant challenges due

to factors such as occlusions, variations in human appearances, illumination, clothing, self-occlusions, and ambiguities inherent to the imaging process [4], [10], [32].

Another categorization considers whether 3D pose estimation methods employ a single or multiple images. Several techniques that process a single RGB image were proposed in the literature with varying degrees of success [10], [15], [16], [20], [28], [30]. However, such techniques face challenges in generating temporally smooth and consistent 3D poses, often leading to unstable and jittery motions [14]. To overcome such issues, video-based techniques with mechanisms, such as self-attention [20], RNNs [4], [7], [14] and 1D temporal convolution networks [11], have been proposed in the literature to maintain temporal consistency and smoothness in 3D human motion. While video-based techniques excel at capturing sequential dependencies, they struggle with long-term ones when encountering complex human motion patterns. Lately, self-attention and Transformer networks have gained significant attention in sequence modeling tasks, including human pose estimation due to their ability to attend to different parts of the input sequence and capture long-range dependencies. Recently, Konstantinidis et al. in [19] moved one step further by incorporating different manifold representations in their multi-manifold self-attention mechanism with the goal to utilize the diverse statistical and geometric characteristics of the input data on different manifolds to improve the discrimination ability of the attention map.

To tackle the aforementioned challenges, we introduce a novel 3D human pose estimation method tailored to capture the complex temporal dynamics of human motion. Our method initially extracts spatial features from input frames prior to the use of two modules to capture the global and local temporal dependencies among the input frames. These modules employ the concept of multi-manifold attention to leverage the rich and complementary information of the input space when projected on different manifolds. Finally, a novel cross-attention mechanism is proposed to fuse the global and local attention maps in each manifold, effectively empowering the model to leverage both broader contextual information and short-term temporal dynamics to create a more comprehensive understanding of temporal sequences. The main contributions of this work are:

- We propose a novel multi-stage 3D human pose and shape estimation method that can accurately model global and local temporal dependencies among image frames,

while simultaneously leveraging descriptive information extracted from different manifolds.

- We introduce a cross-attention mechanism, consisting of a Global and Local Multi-Manifold Self-Attention modules and a Global Contextual module that leverages both broader contextual information and short-term temporal dynamics to create a highly descriptive modeling of temporal sequences.
- We comprehensively evaluate our approach on two well-known datasets, 3DPW [31] and MPI-INF-3DHP [25], demonstrating the superior performance of our proposed methodology compared to other state-of-the-art methods.

II. METHOD

Inspired by the need for a better modeling of the temporal dependencies among image frames for accurate 3D pose estimation, this work proposes a novel cross-attention mechanism that extracts and fuses global and local attention maps, as a means of capturing broader contextual dependencies and short-term temporal dynamics among image frames. The overall architecture of the proposed method is presented in Fig. 1, while a detailed explanation of the different modules follows.

A. Multi-Manifold Self-Attention Block

The aim of this block is to construct a highly descriptive attention map by leveraging the statistical and geometrical properties of different manifolds to produce rich feature representations [19]. To this end, the input feature representation is initially mapped to the Semi-positive definite (SPD) and Grassmann manifolds [5], [6] through the computation of covariance and orthogonal matrices, respectively. The new feature representations can model additional and complementary information in the images, such as texture and color variations. Then, appropriate distance functions are utilized to calculate the distances of the feature representations in the Euclidean, SPD and Grassmann manifolds. The three distinct distance maps are finally fused into a new refined attention map with enhanced modeling capabilities. In this work, we leverage the notion of multi-manifold attention in the video classification context and deviate from the previous usage in image classification tasks.

B. Spatial Feature Extraction

Given a video comprising T RGB frames, i.e., I_1, I_2, \dots, I_T , we initially aim to capture the spatial dependencies residing within each individual frame. To this end, we leverage a pre-trained on ImageNet ResNet-50 model that has been previously fine-tuned in [15] and subsequently use global average pooling as the last layer. This enables us to extract distinctive static frame features, forming a sequence denoted as $\mathbf{S} = \{s_t\}_{t=1}^T$, where $s_t \in \mathbb{R}^d$.

C. Global Multi-Manifold Self-Attention (GMMA) Module

After obtaining the static image features from the previous stage, we shift our focus towards capturing long-range relationships and global dependencies among these features.

To achieve this, we introduce the Global Multi-Manifold Self-Attention (GMMA) module, a pivotal component illustrated in Fig. 2(a). The primary objective of this module is to enhance the contextual understanding of the scene by enabling the network to effectively model the temporal correlations between image features across different frames. The primary building block of this module is the Multi-Manifold Self-Attention block, described in Section II-A, which forms the core mechanism for capturing temporal relationships. Instead of computing spatial correlations among different image patches, this block leverages the high modeling capabilities from the fusion of different manifold representations to identify and model the temporal dynamics present in the input image sequence.

Initially, to mitigate computational complexity, we implement a 1D convolutional operation to project the static spatial features onto a subspace of lower dimensionality, effectively reducing each feature vector’s dimensionality from d to $d/4$. Then, we utilize the Multi-Manifold Self-Attention mechanism to compute attention weights across the temporal sequence. These attention weights play a crucial role in enabling the network to emphasize on frames that are more relevant for the task, while simultaneously reducing the impact of irrelevant frames on the output of the module. This functionality allows the network to effectively capture the global temporal dependencies that exist across the sequence of frames, contributing to an enhanced understanding of the global context. Afterwards, the derived enhanced features are fed to a 1D convolutional layer, effectively reverting them to the initial dimensionality of d . This operation refines and consolidates the features, preparing them for subsequent stages of processing. The output of the global temporal modeling module is the feature matrix $\mathbf{G} \in \mathbb{R}^{T \times d}$.

D. Local Multi-Manifold Self-Attention (LMMA) Module

To address local temporal dependencies, we introduce the Local Multi-Manifold Self-Attention (LMMA) module, depicted in Fig. 2(b). This module facilitates the modeling of short-term relationships among neighboring frames, thereby incorporating local temporal dynamics into the analysis. The process involves taking the global features G and extracting three groups of frames that consist of the intermediary frame, as well as the previous and next frames. The three groups are centered around the middle temporal frame with index $(T/2) + 1$, thus taking into account the frames from index $(T/2) - 3$ to index $(T/2) + 5$, omitting all other frames in the process. Afterwards, each of these three groups are fed to the proposed LMMA module.

In this module, the query, key and value vectors of the attention mechanism are computed as follows. The value vector $V \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times d}$ is the initial concatenation of frames, while the key vector $K \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times d}$ is derived from a linear operation of the concatenated frames. Drawing inspiration from [8], the query vector $Q \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times d}$ is acquired through learnable parameters rather than relying solely on the outcomes of a linear layer. The use of learnable parameters for the computation of the query vector can introduce greater flexibility and adaptability to the

Fig. 1. An overview of the proposed 3D pose estimation method. Given a video sequence, static image features are extracted using a CNN. Subsequently, global dependencies among image features are computed through the Global Multi-Manifold Self-Attention module. Afterwards, a Local Multi-Manifold Self-Attention module exploits short-term relationships (i.e., local dependencies) among neighbouring frames enriched with global contextual information (Global Contextual Module) to enhance the discrimination power of the final local feature representation. Finally, an iterative SMPL parameter regressor and a motion discriminator are utilized to predict the 3D human pose and shape and ensure the smoothness of human movement in the predictions, respectively.

Fig. 2. An overview of (a) the Global Multi-Manifold Self-Attention module and (b) the Local Multi-Manifold Self-Attention module.

learning process, allowing the model to capture more intricate relationships within the data, while concurrently reducing the number of parameters. The query, key and value vectors are then fed to the Multi-Manifold Self-Attention Block, described in Section II-A. It is essential to note that, through the matrix product of the value vector with the result of the self-attention process within the Multi-Manifold Self-Attention Block, each distinct group, $i = 1, 2, 3$, of frames produces a vector $l_i \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times d}$. Finally, the three group representations $l_i, i = 1, 2, 3$ are concatenated together and pass through the same process to produce the final vector $l_{mid} \in \mathbb{R}^d$. This final vector represents the integrated local temporal information and is afterwards processed by the SMPL parameter regressor to produce the final 3d body pose parameters Θ_{mid} .

E. Global Contextual Module

To enhance the discrimination power and classification performance of the proposed model, this work introduces a global contextual module (GCM) that enables the propagation of relevant global contextual information to enhance the local temporal modeling. GCM allows the model to learn how features from a broader context (global attention features) should impact the analysis of local relationships between frames in different groups. To achieve this, GCM consists of a convolutional network that takes the global attention features computed for each manifold in the GMMA module and injects them, using matrix product, into the local attention features computed for the corresponding manifold in the LMMA module. In this way, the local temporal attention of the LMMA module is affected by the global temporal attention

computed by the GMMA module, effectively enabling the fusion of local and global information to achieve improved classification performance.

III. IMPLEMENTATION DETAILS

Following previous works [4], [14], [33], we set the sequence length T to 16 and the feature dimensionality d of ResNet-50 to 2048. Both in training and testing, we utilize ground truth bounding boxes to precisely isolate the human body region. This process entails cropping images of the specified human region, followed by resizing them to dimensions of 224×224 . Regarding the spatial feature extraction process, we pre-compute the image features extracted from ResNet-50 and use them as input to the rest of the model.

Regarding the LMMA module, it should be noted that the network parameters are shared among all groups, as well as during the final integration step. In the case of the GCM, a 2D convolutional layer is employed for each manifold, facilitating the injection of attention features from the GMMA module into each individual LMMA module. Notably, the network parameters of the 2D convolutional layers are shared for each manifold across the three local groups except the final integration step.

With respect to the loss function, during training, we follow the approach outlined by Kocabas et al. [14] for each predicted Θ_{mid} . This approach includes incorporating an L2 loss between the predicted SMPL parameters and the ground truth values, along with the 3D/2D joint coordinates. To obtain the 3D joint coordinates, we feed the predicted SMPL parameters through the SMPL model. As for the 2D joint coordinates, we perform a projection of the corresponding 3D coordinates using the predicted camera parameters.

Furthermore, following previous works [14], [33], we refine our methodology by integrating an adversarial loss, which contributes to the generation of natural and realistic human pose sequences. To achieve this, we employ the AMASS dataset [24], which encompasses a diverse range of genuine human motions. Using this dataset, we train a discriminator to distinguish between two motion types: human motions drawn from the AMASS and the synthesized motions from our framework. Incorporating the adversarial loss enhances the overall quality of the generated poses, leading to a notable improvement in the realism and refinement of the produced 3D human poses.

In terms of optimization, we employ the Adam optimizer [13] with a learning rate set at 1×10^{-4} , contributing to the effective training of our framework. We train our framework for 50 epochs using a single NVIDIA RTX 3090 GPU with 24GB VRAM, and we employ the PyTorch [29] deep learning framework for implementing our method.

IV. EXPERIMENTS

A. Evaluation metrics and datasets

Evaluation metrics. We report our findings on two main categories of evaluation metrics: per-frame and temporal. The

per-frame category includes three metrics: mean per joint position error (MPJPE), Procrustes-aligned MPJPE (PA-MPJPE), and mean per vertex position error (MPVPE). These metrics quantify the disparity, in millimeters (mm), between the predicted 3D coordinates, after aligning the root joint, and the ground truth coordinates. It should be noted that PA-MPJPE is considered as the main metric regarding the first evaluation category, since it mitigates the impact of errors due to the scale ambiguity of the output [14]. Additionally, we employ the acceleration error (ACC-ERR) as discussed in [11], which characterizes the temporal coherence and steadiness of 3D human motion. This metric measures the differences between predicted and ground truth accelerations for each joint, and it is expressed in units of mm/s^2 .

Datasets. Following previous works [4], [14], [33] our proposed method is trained on mixed batches of 3D and 2D datasets. Regarding the 3D datasets, we utilize 3DPW [31], MPI-INF-3DHP [25], Human3.6M [9], and AMASS [24] during the training process. As for the 2D datasets, we employ PoseTrack [2] and InstaVariety [11]. For the evaluation of the proposed method, we use the 3DPW and MPI-INF-3DHP datasets.

B. Ablation Study

In this section, we delve into the distinct contributions of each introduced component by evaluating the proposed method across various configurations. We conduct ablation study on the challenging 3DPW [31] dataset, effectively gauging the effects of each element. We subject the input RGB frames to identical transformations as described above. The experimental findings are comprehensively detailed in Table I.

Impact of the Global Contextual module. To investigate the effectiveness of the proposed GCM, we perform a comparative analysis of the model’s performance, considering scenarios both with and without the integration of GCM. As shown in Table I, it is evident that the inclusion of GCM improves the performance of the model across all evaluation metrics. More specifically, the PA-MPJPE error is reduced by 0.95, while the MPJPE drops by 0.85 when GCM is employed. These results verify that GCM can enhance the model’s capacity to capture intricate global and local temporal correlations among image frames, selectively emphasize salient temporal regions and align crucial visual cues through the fusion of global and local attention maps.

Impact of LMMA module. The introduction of the LMMA module enables the model to focus on capturing short-term temporal dependencies among neighboring frames. As highlighted in Table I, the LMMA module plays a crucial role to the performance of the model by enabling it to better model the short-term temporal dynamics within the sequence of frames. Without this module, the model experiences a deterioration of over 186% in the relative value of the acceleration error, as well as an increase of around 2% in the other error metrics. These results further support the significance of modeling global and local temporal correlations among image frames for the task of 3D pose estimation.

TABLE I
ABLATION STUDY ON THE 3DPW [31] DATASET

Model	3DPW			
	PA-MPJPE ↓	MPJPE ↓	MPVPE ↓	ACC-ERR ↓
Proposed w/o Global Contextual Module	52.75	85.32	100.79	7.48
Proposed w/o LMMA module	53.26	85.84	102.20	21.31
Proposed w/o Multi-Manifold self-attention block	52.90	85.42	100.66	7.45
Proposed	51.80	84.47	100.09	7.44

TABLE II
COMPARISON AGAINST STATE-OF-THE-ART VIDEO-BASED METHODS ON 3DPW [31] AND MPI-INF-3DHP [25] DATASETS. WITH THE EXCEPTION OF HMMR [11], ALL OTHER METHODS UTILIZE 3DPW FOR TRAINING BUT DO NOT INCORPORATE HUMAN3.6M SMPL PARAMETERS FROM MOSH [21]

Method	3DPW				MPI-INF-3DHP			Number of input frames
	PA-MPJPE ↓	MPJPE ↓	MPVPE ↓	ACC-ERR ↓	PA-MPJPE ↓	MPJPE ↓	ACC-ERR ↓	
HMMR [11]	72.6	116.5	139.3	15.2	-	-	-	20
VIBE [14]	57.6	91.9	-	25.4	68.9	103.9	27.3	16
MEVA [23]	54.7	86.9	-	11.6	65.4	96.4	11.1	90
TCMR [4]	52.7	86.5	103.2	6.8	63.5	97.6	8.5	16
MPS-Net [33]	52.1	84.3	99.7	7.4	62.8	96.7	9.6	16
Proposed	51.8	84.47	100.09	7.44	62.46	98.23	8.62	16

Impact of Multi-Manifold Self-Attention block. To assess the importance of incorporating multiple manifolds into the Multi-Manifold Self-Attention Block, an additional experiment is conducted, during which we either use all three manifolds or employ solely the Euclidean manifold, as performed in the vanilla attention mechanism of standard Transformer network architectures. As seen in Table I, the use of the multi-manifold attention mechanism leads to a reduction of all error metrics, with PA-MPJPE dropping from 52.9 to 51.8 and MPJPE dropping from 85.42 to 84.47. This outcome highlights the significance of the multi-manifold approach in the proposed model. By incorporating multiple manifolds, the model gains the capacity to capture diverse and intricate data relationships that exist beyond the constraints of the Euclidean space. The experiment reinforces the idea that actions and poses encompass non-linear dynamics that are better captured by considering multiple geometric structures simultaneously.

C. Comparison with state-of-the-art approaches

A comparison between the proposed method and other state-of-the-art video-based 3D pose estimation methods is performed in Table II. From the results, it can be seen that the proposed method outperforms the other approaches in the PA-MPJPE metric, which is considered the most important metric in 3D pose estimation, in both 3DPW and MPI-INF-3DZHP datasets, while achieving satisfactory results in the other metrics. From Table II, it can be observed that most 3D pose estimation methods prioritize either spatial consistency (i.e., improvement of metrics PA-MPJPE, MPJPE and MPVPE), such as the method of MPS-Net, or temporal consistency (i.e., improvement of ACC-ERR metric), such as the method of TCMR. With the extraction of highly descriptive global and local temporal information, the proposed method strikes a balance between spatial and temporal consistency by outperforming MPS-Net in the spatial dimension, while retaining a performance close to the TCMR in the temporal

Fig. 3. 3D pose estimation results from the proposed method.

dimension. Finally, a visualization of the results of the proposed method in a video sequence from the 3DPW dataset is presented in Fig. 3. These results further support the high accuracy and robustness of the proposed method in 3D pose and shape estimation.

V. CONCLUSION

This work introduces a novel video-based multi-stage 3D human pose and shape estimation method that relies on the extraction of global and local temporal dependencies among input frames. By harnessing the power of various manifold representations, the proposed method is capable of extracting highly descriptive local and global attention maps, while the novel cross-attention mechanism combines these attention maps, effectively integrating the global contextual information in the local temporal information, significantly improving the ability of the model in capturing both short-term and long-term dependencies across image frames. Experimental results on two well-known datasets and against state-of-the-art techniques verify the increased accuracy and robustness of the proposed method.

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